

Analysis of Risk Factors and Mapping of Helminth Infection Incidence in the Working Area of Nulle Public Health Center, South Central Timor Regency

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ABSTRACT

Background: Soil-Transmitted Helminth (STH) infections remain a public health concern in tropical regions, particularly among school-aged children, while local data and risk mapping in the service area of Nulle Primary Health Center are limited.

Objective: To estimate the prevalence of STH infection, identify water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH)-related risk factors, and spatially map infection clusters among primary schoolchildren in South Central Timor, Indonesia.

Methods: A cross-sectional survey was conducted in seven primary schools from 10–16 June 2025, involving 263 students. Data on WASH-related behaviors and environmental conditions were collected using structured questionnaires. Stool samples were examined using the direct smear method with 2% eosin and 2% lugol's iodine. Bivariate analysis was performed using Fisher's exact test with $\alpha = 0.05$. Geographic household coordinates of STH-positive cases were mapped using ArcGIS to identify spatial clusters.

Results: The prevalence of helminth infection was 4.6% (12/263). The most common species identified was *Ascaris lumbricoides* (83.3%), followed by *Trichuris trichiura* and mixed infections (each 8.3%). Handwashing habits, nail trimming, consumption of raw food, use of footwear, latrine ownership, and household water source were significantly associated with infection ($p < 0.05$). GIS mapping revealed high-risk areas in Nulle, Tublopo, and Benlutu villages, characterized by high soil humidity, suitable temperature and soil type, as well as poor sanitation conditions.

Conclusion: STH infection in the Nulle area remains a concern, influenced by hygiene behaviors and environmental conditions. Location-based promotive and preventive efforts are essential to reduce infection rates.

KEYWORDS: Soil-transmitted helminths, schoolchildren, WASH, risk factors, GIS.

INTRODUCTION

Soil-transmitted helminth (STH) infections, primarily caused by *Ascaris lumbricoides*, *Trichuris trichiura*, and hookworms, represent a significant global disease burden and disproportionately affect school-aged children in tropical and subtropical regions with inadequate water, sanitation, and hygiene (WASH) infrastructure.¹ Chronic infections may lead to malnutrition, iron-deficiency anemia, growth retardation, and impaired cognitive development, ultimately affecting educational outcomes and economic potential.² In Indonesia, STH infections remain endemic in many rural areas, with prevalence influenced by socioeconomic conditions, environmental factors, and local hygiene practices.³

The province of East Nusa Tenggara (NTT), including South Central Timor Regency, is characterized by a dry-land climate; however, several agroecological zones with irrigation and higher soil moisture create favorable conditions for the survival and transmission of soil-transmitted helminth (STH) eggs and larvae.⁴ Although national deworming programs have been implemented, their effectiveness may be limited without simultaneous improvements in WASH conditions, as evidenced by high reinfection rates reported under similar circumstances.⁵ Systematic reviews and meta-analyses consistently demonstrate the protective effects of improved water quality, adequate sanitation facilities, and good hygiene practices against STH infection.^{6,7}

Nevertheless, specific local determinants and spatial variation within the Nulle Primary Health Center catchment area remain insufficiently documented.

Geographic Information Systems (GIS) serve as a powerful tool to visualize the spatial distribution of diseases, identify high-risk clusters, and support targeted intervention strategies. Integrating epidemiological data with spatial analysis can reveal environmental and behavioral relationships with infection at a more granular scale, which is essential for efficient resource allocation.⁸ Therefore, this study aims to: (1) estimate the prevalence of STH infection among elementary school children in the Nulle Primary Health Center area; (2) analyze associations between WASH-related behavioral and environmental factors and STH infection; and (3) map the spatial distribution of cases to identify potential high-risk clusters as a basis for targeted public health interventions.

METHODS

This research employed an analytical cross-sectional design and was conducted from June 10 to 16, 2025, in the Nulle Primary Health Center catchment area, located in Amanuban Barat Subdistrict, South Central Timor Regency, East Nusa Tenggara Province, Indonesia. The study population consisted of elementary school students enrolled in seven purposively selected schools within the region. A total of 263 children aged 6–12 years were included based on eligibility criteria, namely obtaining parental consent and submitting a stool sample. Participants were excluded if they had received anthelmintic medication within the preceding three months or were unable to complete the questionnaire. Written informed consent was obtained from parents or guardians, and assent was additionally provided by each child prior to participation.

Data collection utilized two primary instruments. First, structured questionnaires completed by parents or guardians were used to obtain information on sociodemographic characteristics, household WASH conditions, and child hygiene practices, including handwashing, nail trimming, footwear use, playing habits, food consumption, and deworming history. Second, stool samples were collected in sterile labeled containers and examined within several hours in a field laboratory. Direct smear techniques using 2% eosin and 2% Lugol's iodine were prepared on separate slides and evaluated under light microscopy at 100x and 400x magnification by trained laboratory personnel to identify the presence of soil-transmitted helminth eggs.

Geospatial information was also integrated into the study. The geographic coordinates of households of STH-positive children were recorded using the Avenza Maps® GPS-enabled mobile application, following parental permission. The collected data were analyzed using appropriate statistical software. Descriptive statistics summarized baseline characteristics and STH prevalence, which was reported with 95% confidence intervals based on the exact Clopper-Pearson method. Associations between WASH-related variables and infection status were examined using Fisher's exact test, considering small cell counts in several categories with a significance threshold of $\alpha = 0.05$. Spatial datasets were imported into ArcGIS (version 10.x) to generate point distribution maps, and preliminary cluster assessment was performed through visual interpretation of case dispersion over village boundary overlays.

This study received ethical approval from the Health Research Ethics Committee of the Faculty of Medicine and Veterinary Medicine, Universitas Nusa Cendana, Kupang (Reference Number: 23/UN15.21/KEPK-FKKH/2025), and all procedures complied with institutional standards for research involving human participants and conformed to the principles of the Declaration of Helsinki.

RESULT

Univariate analysis described the characteristics of respondents including age, sex, school distribution, STH infection status, helminth species, hygiene behaviors, eating habits, sanitation practices, and environmental factors. The study involved seven elementary schools (GMIT Nulle, Inpres Neonmat, Inpres Nulle, Oenali, Tanah Merah, Oekamusa, and Oe'usapi) with an initial population of 330 students. A total of 67 children were excluded due to absence of stool samples or submission of inappropriate samples, resulting in a final sample size of 263 participants.

Microscopic examination showed an overall prevalence of STH infection of 4.6% (12/263). The infection was predominantly caused by *Ascaris lumbricoides* (3.8%, 10/263), followed by single *Trichuris trichiura* infection (0.4%, 1/263) and mixed infection (0.4%, 1/263). Most children reported handwashing hygiene; however, 64.3% (169/263) did not practice the complete seven-step handwashing technique, 31.6% (83/263) did not trim nails regularly, and nail-biting or finger-sucking behaviors were still common.

Bivariate analysis using Fisher’s exact test revealed several behavioral and environmental factors significantly associated with STH infection. Handwashing without soap, not washing hands after defecation, not trimming nails weekly, consumption of raw/unwashed food, lack of footwear use, soil-playing habits, open defecation, unprotected water sources, and not boiling water showed statistically significant associations ($p < 0.05$). Deworming every six months demonstrated a protective effect.

Table 1. Distribution of respondent characteristics, STH prevalence, and bivariate analysis results

Variable	Category	N (%)	OR	95% CI	p-value
Total respondents	-	263 (100%)	-	-	-
Age	6–7 years	18 (6.8)	-	-	-
	8–9 years	68 (25.9)	-	-	-
	10–11 years	147 (55.9)	-	-	-
	12–13 years	30 (11.4)	-	-	-
Sex	Male	123 (46.8)	-	-	-
	Female	140 (53.2)	-	-	-
STH Status	Positive	12 (4.6)	-	-	-
	Negative	251 (95.4)	-	-	-
Species	<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i>	10 (3.8)	-	-	-
	<i>Trichuris trichiura</i>	1 (0.4)	-	-	-
	Mixed infection	1 (0.4)	-	-	-
	Negative	251 (95.4)	-	-	-
Hand Hygiene	No handwashing before meals	33 (12.5)	0.009	0.001–0.071	<0.001
	Handwashing before meals (Ref)	230 (87.5)	Ref	-	-
	No soap used	57 (21.7)	-	-	<0.001
	With soap (Ref)	206 (78.3)	Ref	-	-
	No handwashing after defecation	32 (12.2)	0.008	0.001–0.071	<0.001
	Handwashing after defecation (Ref)	231 (87.8)	Ref	-	-
	Incomplete 7-step technique	169 (64.3)	-	-	-
	Complete technique (Ref)	94 (35.7)	Ref	-	-
Nail Hygiene	No weekly nail trimming	83 (31.6)	0.082	0.018–0.384	<0.001
	Weekly nail trimming (Ref)	180 (68.4)	Ref	-	-
	No nail-biting	59 (22.4)	0.187	0.057–0.612	0.002
	Nail-biting (Ref)	204 (77.6)	Ref	-	-
	No finger sucking	59 (22.4)	0.384	0.117–1.257	0.148
	Finger sucking (Ref)	204 (77.6)	Ref	-	-
Defecation Practices	No latrine use	7 (2.7)	0.024	0.005–0.127	<0.001
	Latrine use (Ref)	256 (97.3)	Ref	-	-
	Open defecation (Yes)	83 (31.6)	0.184	0.056–0.600	0.002
	No open defecation (Ref)	180 (68.4)	Ref	-	-

Variable	Category	N (%)	OR	95% CI	p-value
Eating Habits	Consumption of raw food	78 (29.7)	0.089	0.019–0.414	<0.001
	Cooked food (Ref)	185 (70.3)	Ref	-	-
	Washing raw food (Yes)	32 (12.2)	0.126	0.038–0.416	<0.001
	No washing (Ref)	231 (87.8)	Ref	-	-
Foot Hygiene	No footwear	52 (19.8)	-	-	<0.001
	With footwear (Ref)	211 (80.2)	Ref	-	-
	No foot washing after soil exposure	45 (17.1)	0.056	0.014–0.216	0.002
	Foot washing (Ref)	218 (82.9)	Ref	-	-
Deworming Practice	No deworming every 6 months	20 (7.6)	0.136	0.037–0.501	0.008
	Deworming (Ref)	243 (92.4)	Ref	-	-
Environmental Sanitation	Earthen floor	51 (19.4)	0.314	0.095–1.034	0.060
	Cement/ceramic (Ref)	212 (80.6)	Ref	-	-
	No household toilet	6 (2.3)	0.258	0.078–0.853	0.033
	With toilet (Ref)	257 (97.7)	Ref	-	-
	Pit latrine	44 (16.7)	0.258	0.078–0.853	0.033
Water Source	Goose-neck latrine (Ref)	219 (83.3)	Ref	-	-
	Unprotected river	27 (10.3)	0.062	0.018–0.213	<0.001
	Protected PDAM (Ref)	236 (89.7)	Ref	-	-
	No boiling drinking water	7 (2.7)	0.011	0.002–0.068	<0.001
	Boiled drinking water (Ref)	256 (97.3)	Ref	-	-

Notes: Ref = reference category used for comparison in odds ratio estimation. OR expresses the likelihood of STH infection relative to the reference group. Variables with zero cell counts were analyzed with Fisher’s exact test.

Based on bivariate analysis using Fisher’s exact test, hand hygiene behavior, nail cleanliness, and nail-biting habits showed a significant association with STH infection ($p < 0.001$). Children who did not wash their hands before eating or after defecation, did not use soap, or did not perform proper handwashing steps had a higher likelihood of infection. Failure to trim nails weekly was also associated with increased infection risk. The presence of $OR < 1$ for these variables indicates a protective effect of proper hygiene behaviors. Thumb or finger-sucking habits were not statistically significant ($p = 0.148$). Defecation practices were significantly associated with STH infection. Not using a latrine ($p < 0.001$, $OR = 0.024$) and practicing open defecation ($p = 0.002$, $OR = 0.184$) increased infection risk, indicating the protective role of latrine use in preventing transmission. Environmental sanitation also demonstrated an effect, particularly the type of toilet used ($p = 0.033$, $OR = 0.258$; 95% CI: 0.078–0.853), where pour-flush toilets were more protective compared to pit latrines. Dietary and drinking-water practices contributed to infection outcomes. Consumption of raw food increased the risk (11.5% vs 1.1%; $OR = 0.089$; $p < 0.001$), while washing raw foods reduced it ($OR = 0.126$; $p < 0.001$). Boiling drinking water demonstrated a strong protective effect ($OR = 0.011$; $p < 0.001$), and routine deworming every six months reduced infection rates ($p = 0.008$; $OR = 0.136$). Use of unprotected river water was associated with a higher infection rate (25.9% vs 2.1%; $p < 0.001$; $OR = 0.062$).

Figure 1. Spatial distribution of STH cases in the Nulle Health Center area

Spatial mapping of soil-transmitted helminth infections within the Nulle Primary Health Center catchment area revealed that cases were not evenly distributed, but clustered in several villages including Nulle, Tublopo, Pusu, Tubuhue, and Benlutu. These patterns indicate the role of environmental factors in influencing disease distribution, suggesting that particular ecological characteristics support helminth egg survival and transmission. The identified clusters provide a basis for prioritizing high-risk areas for targeted interventions. Most positive cases were located near forest, garden, paddy fields, and river zones with moist environments, which favor the development of *Ascaris lumbricoides* and *Trichuris trichiura* eggs. Loose agricultural soil and community activities such as playing or working barefoot increased exposure to contaminated soil. Microclimate variation also contributed to spatial differences, where wetland zones were associated with mixed *Ascaris*–*Trichuris* infection, while drier zones were dominated by *Ascaris*. Temperature, humidity, and soil type were determining factors, and therefore the spatial analysis supports the need for geographically tailored public health strategies, including sanitation improvement, clean water provision, and hygiene education.

DISCUSSION

Prevalence and Parasite Profile

Among the 263 school-aged children examined, 12 were identified as positive for STH infection, resulting in an overall prevalence of 4.6% (95% CI: 2.4–7.8%). This prevalence is lower than that reported in several other regions in Indonesia and comparable tropical areas, which may reflect the impact of routine mass drug administration programs and the predominantly dry-land ecological characteristics in parts of the study area.^{9,10} *Ascaris lumbricoides* constituted the predominant species detected (10 cases, 83.3%), followed by a single case of *Trichuris trichiura* (8.3%) and one mixed *A. lumbricoides*–*T. trichiura* infection (8.3%). The dominance of ascariasis aligns with environmental persistence and transmission biology, which is strongly influenced by soil contamination from human feces.¹ These findings support the sustained benefit of periodic mass deworming programs among school-age children. The absence of hookworm infection may reflect relatively good footwear-use habits and high deworming coverage in the study population.^{5,6,10}

Association With WASH and Behavioral Factors

Bivariate analysis revealed significant associations between STH infection and water, sanitation, hygiene (WASH) practices. Key protective behaviors included regular handwashing with soap before eating and after defecation ($p < 0.01$), correct seven-step handwashing technique ($p < 0.01$), weekly nail trimming ($p < 0.001$), consistent consumption of boiled drinking water ($p < 0.001$), and preference for cooked food over raw food ($p < 0.01$). These results emphasize the importance of personal hygiene in interrupting the fecal–oral transmission route of STH, consistent with global evidence.^{6,11}

Environmental and household-level protective factors were also identified. The use of pour-flush latrines showed a significant association with lower infection risk compared to pit latrines ($p=0.033$), while access to protected water sources such as piped or bore water was associated with reduced infection likelihood compared to unprotected river water ($p<0.001$). Deworming within the last six months also showed a protective effect ($p=0.008$). The link between improved sanitation and lower STH prevalence is strongly supported by meta-analytic findings.⁷ Associations with water source further highlight two principal transmission pathways—waterborne exposure and soil-mediated infection—consistent with local reports on water quality challenges in the region.¹²

Spatial Distribution and Clustering

GIS-based mapping analysis demonstrated distinct spatial clustering of STH cases. Infections were not randomly distributed but concentrated in several villages, particularly Nulle, Tublopo, Pusu, Tubuhue, and Benlutu. These clusters are likely shaped by environmental characteristics such as higher soil moisture, proximity to water bodies or irrigation zones, communal defecation areas, and shared socio-behavioral patterns within communities.

Figure 2. Spatial Distribution and Clustering of STH Cases

Most infections occurred near forest, garden, rice field, and river environments with high humidity, conditions favorable for *A. lumbricoides* egg development at 25–30°C and approximately 80% humidity, and *T. trichiura* eggs at 28–30°C and around 87% humidity. Moist, loose soil enhances egg viability, while barefoot outdoor activities increase contact with contaminated soil.¹³ These findings support targeted intervention based on spatial prioritization, particularly in wet-land agricultural zones and river-adjacent settlements.

CONCLUSION

This study found a relatively low yet persistent prevalence of soil-transmitted helminth (STH) infection (4.6%) among school-aged children in South Central Timor, with *Ascaris lumbricoides* as the dominant parasite. Infection remained strongly associated with inadequate WASH conditions and risky hygiene behaviors, including lack of footwear use, frequent soil contact, open defecation practices, and reliance on unprotected water sources. In contrast, protective behaviors such as proper handwashing with soap, routine nail trimming, and consumption of safe food and boiled drinking water were significantly associated with reduced infection risk.

Spatial analysis identified village-level clustering, providing clear geographic targets for intervention. These findings emphasize the need for an integrated control strategy. While mass deworming programs using albendazole or mebendazole, as mandated by national policy,¹⁴ should continue, sustainable impact will require community-driven improvements in access to protected water sources, promotion of safe sanitation facilities (preferably pour-flush latrines), and reinforcement of key hygiene behaviors. Integrating WASH interventions with deworming, specifically within the identified spatial clusters, may yield the greatest public health impact and contribute to sustainable interruption of STH transmission in this region.

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